

Social Studies Education: Panacea for Tackling Corruption in Nigeria at Basic Level of Education

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Abstract

This Study is aimed to Examine Social Studies Education Panacea for Tackling Corruption in Nigeria at basic level of education. Social Studies is the subject saddled with the responsibility to contribute in tackling the social, economic, and political problems in Nigeria. The thrust of the paper is to discuss the concept of Social Studies, Philosophy of Social Studies, Objectives of Social Studies, the paper also discussed the concept of corruption, types of corruption, causes of corruption, social implication of corruption, educational implication of corruption in Nigeria and Social Studies education panacea for tackling corruption in Nigeria at basic level of education. The paper concluded that the causes of corruption in Nigeria are: political interference, lack or inadequate welfare package, greediness, selfishness among others. The paper also identified that the implication of corruption in Nigeria are: it slows down economic development and produces unproductive graduates. The paper has the following suggestion: Attitudinal change, Teaching of Social Studies, Good Leadership, Strict and severe punishment, Welfare package, creating awareness on the dangers of corruption.

Keywords: Social Studies, Education, Panacea, Corruption

Introduction

Corruption is one of the social problems that is bedeviling Nigerian and could be found in all the sectors. Corruption is innate and deep seated in Nigeria particularly in the public sector (Okolo and Raymond, 2014). Corruption is any act or behavior or omission, committed intentionally or not to influence the action of another, the influential and the influenced respectively has corrupted a system which is detrimental to the entire society (Okolo and Raymond, 2014). Corruption is a behavior which deviates from the formal duties of a public role because of pecuniary or status gains which violates rules against the exercise of certain types of influence (Aigbengbe, 2010). It implies that is a bad attitude of greediness and selfishness exhibited by the perpetrator. This act has become the order of the day in Nigeria and many countries of the world and made Nigeria to be rated 24 out of 100 as put forward by (Transparency International, 2023). This clearly indicated that Nigeria are yet to get out of the Menace of corruption because there is corruption in all spheres of our lives which could be attributed to various factors as put forward by different scholars. The purpose of this paper therefore, is to identify the causes as well as socio-economic, and educational implications of corruption in Nigeria with the view to tackle it from Social Studies angle. According to (Adeboye and Obaje, 2016) the causes of corruption in Nigeria are: greediness, poor reward system, wrong home training, peer influence, poor condition of service. (Ribadu in Tikuma 2009) posited that the causes of corruption in Nigeria could be traced to the 29 years of military rule in Nigeria. Others blame it to tribal and ethnic factors as the fountain of Nigeria corruption. Corruption has eaten deep into the fabric of almost all Nigerian society which in turn threatened the socio-economic growth and development of the country. Corruption is a stigma that destroys the reputation of affected country. It lowers investment there by lowering economic growth of the country (Ola, 2014). Nigeria society encourages corrupt practices and this is higher at the basic educational level. Teachers encourage corruption through extortion, collection

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of gifts items, receiving of bribes and unethical favoritism. Corruption causes a reduction in quality of teaching and learning as many teachers are not rewarded the way they should. A corollary of corruption is late payment, delays or refusals in payment for services already rendered what directly impacts on the country's educational enterprises (Adeboye and Obaje, 2016) hence, the need for the Social Studies Education panacea for tackling corruption in Nigeria.

Concept of Social Studies

Definitions varies according to situations, aspirations and expectation of the people. A critical analysis of the definition of Social Studies in Educational literature indicated that Social Studies Education has been defined in the following ways: Irmiya and Bitrus (2019) express Social Studies as an integrated subject that exposes learners to desirable knowledge, attitude, values and skills necessary for effective socio-civic life. Aigbangbe (2010) opined that Social Studies education is a problem solving course of study. It deals with societal issues and problems and prescribes effective ways of solving them. Nwanko (2018) Social Studies education would produce detribalized, patriotic, flexible and objective citizens who could be able to adapt to changes in order to suit the prevailing needs and interest of the nation. Thus Social Studies education helps in three critical areas of values oriented education, civil Education and Environmental education. Uzokife and Obaje (2022) submitted that Social Studies education among other school subject is primarily design an taught in schools to address issues relating to tight type of values, attitudes and behavior with a view to achieving sustainable development. Farmson (2020) posited that Social Studies is meant to provide coordinated, systematic study which draws upon such disciplines as anthropology, economics, geography, history, law philosophy, political science religion and sociology, as well as appropriate contents from the humanities, mathematics and natural science. Social Studies is a comprehensive adequate and total study of man in his environment with the aim to lead realizes the potentials and uses them to solve various problems. Thus, social, economic and political problems could be solved using the subject of Social Studies. Through the teaching of good values of selflessness, contentment, justice, tolerance, fair play, positives attitude, and self-reliant etc.

Philosophy of Social Studies Education

The philosophy of Social Studies presupposes that the curriculum package envisaged in this “functionality principle” necessarily demands that Social Studies education need to be problem solving; it must not only possess a relative and transfer value but to display a purpose that relates to life situations (Aderalege, 1980). These criteria of the philosophy of social that Social Studies represent a relevant curriculum package which aims at integrating many related subject areas and discipline which offer to the young learners a “holistic” portrait of a man and his knowledge of society. Social Studies should not only be Nigerian in orientation but must portrait her as a dynamic and developing society. Based on this philosophy, young learners need to be equipped not only with necessary tools for making their own contributions in terms of societal changes but also giving directions of these changes that the framework of Nigeria. This philosophy must be actively oriented and need to offer learners the opportunity to practice skills which will assist them function effectively at school and in life situation (Okam, 1998)

Objectives of Social Studies Education

Social studies as stated earlier was introduced into Nigerian schools and made a core or compulsory subject at primary and junior secondary schools to help achieve the four national educational aims and objectives namely:

1. The inculcation of national consciousness and national unity.
2. The inculcation of the right type of values and attitudes for the survival of the individual and the Nigerian society.
3. The training of the mind in the understanding of the world around, and
4. The acquisition of appropriate skills, abilities and competencies both mental and physical as equipment for the individual to live in and contribute to the development of his society.

In line with the above national educational aims and objectives, social studies educators and educationalists in Nigeria formulated among others the following general objectives of social studies educators and educationists in Nigeria formulated among others the following general objectives of social studies teaching in schools:

- i. To create an awareness and an understanding of our evolving social and physical environment as a whole in its natural, manmade, cultural and spiritual resources for national development.
- ii. To develop a capacity to learn and to acquire certain basic skills, including not only those of listening, speaking, reading, writing and of calculation, but also those skills of hand and head together with those of observation, analysis, and inferences which are essential for making sound social economic and political judgment.

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- iii. To ensure the acquisition of that relevant body of body of knowledge and information which is an essential pre-requisite to personal development as well as to a positive personal contribution to the betterment of mankind.
- iv. To develop a sympathetic appreciation of the diversity and inter-dependence of all members of the local community, and the wider national and international community.
- v. To develop in students positive attitudes of togetherness, comradeship and co-operation towards a healthy nation; the inculcation of appropriate values of honesty, integrity, hard work, fairness and justice at work and play as one's contribution to the development of the nation.
- vi. To encourage learners to appreciate that all the things they have learnt are interrelated through social studies it is possible to present knowledge as a whole instead of a series of specialized fragments.

To achieve the above national educational aims and objectives and the formulated general studies objectives in schools, there is the need for proper education and re-education of social studies teachers in the areas of methodology and evaluation strategies. There is also the need for production of relevant text books and other instructional materials. Equally importance is that teachers and students should be provided with conducive atmosphere for effective teaching and learning process. (Argungu, 2000)

Concept of Corruption

Oganwu (2016) defined Corruption as deviation from existing norm for personal benefit. Omale mumini and salisu (2018) see it as a form of dishonesty or unethical conduct by a person entrusted with a position of authority, often to acquire personal benefit. Adebayo Funsho and Obaje (2020) submitted that corruption is a behavior which deviates from the formal duties of a public role because of pecuniary or status gains which violates rules against the exercise of certain types of influence Jarome and Anekwe (2022) View it as; allowing self to get influenced for personal interest at the detriment of the need of the society. Dramola (2020) posited it as a social phenomenon which manifests in various human actions such as deceit, wickedness, selfishness, embezzlement of public fund or property, which could be described as primitive accumulation of wealth, moral degradation, bribery, insatiability, covetousness etc. Wikipedia (2017) defined it as form of dishonesty or unethical behavior by a person(s) entrusted with position of authority. Ekechukwu (2021) opined Corruption as dishonest, illegal or moral behaviors carried out by those in positions of authority or entrusted with something or an office. It is an irresponsible unmatured behavior displayed by trusted people for personal gains. This act is needed to be arrested in all respects before it consume the entire nation.

Types of Corruption

According to Aigbangbe (2010) Corruption can be categorized into the following:

1. **Bribery:** This involves the payment (in money or kind) that is taken or given in a corrupt relationship and includes kickbacks, gratitude, pay off, sweeteners, greasing palms etc.
2. **Fraud:** This involves some kind of trickery, swindle and deceit, counterfeiting, racketing, smuggling and forgery.
3. **Embezzlement:** This is the theft of public resources by public officials. It is when a state official steals from the public institution in which he is employed. This is very common in Nigeria.
4. **Extortion:** This is money and other resources extracted by the use of coercion, violence or threat. It is often seen as extraction from below (the police and custom officials are the main culprits in Nigeria but things are changing now)
5. **Favoritism:** This is a mechanism of power abuse implying a highly brazed distribution of state resources to favored friends, family members and close associates
6. **Nepotism:** This is a special form of favoritism in which an office holder prefers his /her kinfolk and family members. This occurs when one is exempted from the application of certain laws or regulations or given undue preference in the allocation of scarce resources.

Causes of Corruption

Adebayo et'al (2020) maintained that the root cause of this evil is materialism, so materialism is the only cause for quest for corruption in education. A society which glorifies the fruits of materialism inevitably sow the seeds of corruption. In the same vein tikuma (2009) indicated that factors responsible for corruption in Nigeria are: poor salaries and social welfare, departure from traditional economic system, self-aggrandizement. Adebayo and Obaje (2016) maintained that it is common to see that when the government does not cater for all the basic needs of the people any more, there is tendency for people to get corrupted inorder to be able to cater for such needs. Greediness, poor reward system, wrong home training, peer influence, poor condition of service. Ola (2014) alluded that the causes of corruption in Nigeria are: Low civil service salaries and poor working

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conditions, with few incentives and rewards for efficient and effective performance, are strong incentives for corruption in Nigeria. Other factors are less effective government works with slow budget procedure, lack of transparency, inadequate strategies vision and weak monitoring mechanisms make a Nigeria a fertile the environment for corrupt practices. Aigbangbe (2010) maintained that the causes of corruption in Nigeria can be summed up as great inequality in distribution of wealth; political office as primary means of access to wealth; conflict between changing moral code; the weakness of social and government law enforcement mechanism, the get rich quick syndrome, poor welfare package, influence of peer group and the absence of a strong sense of national pride.

Socio-Economic implication of corruption in Nigeria

Rosemary and Bonmwa (2014) posited that massive and extensive corruption in Nigeria has depleted the stock of capital requisite for development just as it does in any other political economy. Corruption had severe negative consequences on the economic growth and development of Nigeria. Where improper conducts such as fraud and bribery are prevalent, the public effects and severe. Corruption has adversely affected governance and the larger social structure. It has crippled the nation's ability to deliver for it citizens' welfare of even their minimum social and economic right. This generally has led to a retardation of economic of economic development and deterioration whatever public infrastructure has been put in place. According to Peter Sunday and Ndem (2012) maintained that corrupt economic practices tend to increase the cost of doing business in the country. The corrupt resources transferred abroad or used for importation of non- essential good act as drain on the economy, depriving it of the ability to generate jobs for people domestically. In another sense the smuggling of foreign made products can cause unemployment by undercutting the competitive sales of the existing legitimate industries there by forcing them to operate under capacity. When a corrupt socio-political-ecomomic system enthrones mediocrity in position of leadership, a vicious system of mediocrity emerges and this tends to be self-perpetuating. Corruption has led to a chronic deficit in Nigeria balance of payments both directly and indirectly. Indirectly the leakage-effects corruption imposes on GDP can jeopardize the country's balance of payments positions. Corruption tends to generate and perpetuate distributional inequality in both economic and political powers in a society. The effectiveness of economic policies can be seriously undermined by corruption as is currently the case in Nigeria. Adebayo and Obaje (2016) pointed out that corruption has eaten deep into the fabric of almost all Nigerian society, which has inturn threatened the economic growth and development of the country. Corruption has destroyed the value system of Nigerian society and is killing the conscience of the nation. Ola (2014) opined that corruption stiple economic growth, reduced economic efficiency and development despite the enomous resources in the country. Corruption creates negative national image and loss of much needed revenue. It devalues the quality of human life, robs schools, agricultural sectors, hospital and welfare services of funds. Corruption is a stigma that destroys the reputation of affected country. It lowers investment there by lowering economic growth of the country. Bamboye (2018) realizes that the impact of corruption include among others, poor economic growth, poor infrastructural development, underutilization of human and natural resources distorted policies and poor policy implementation and a colossal loss of public funds and poor in flow of foreign direct investment. The issue of corruption in Nigeria is endemic and pervasive, with negative impact on all facet of the country. Ekechuku (2021) submitted that corruption has ravaged all the sectors in Nigeria and it is responsible for the under development, economic and social crisis witnessed all over the country. It has become a societal norm and an acceptable way of life to the extent that corrupt people are celebrated and recognized by awarding chieftancy titles to them or appointment into public offices. The various government at all levels have failed due to this cankerworm that has eaten up the whole country.

Educational Implication of Corruption in Nigeria

Elem (2019) Opined that corruption in educational sector in Nigeria is responsible for the low standard of education in the country. As a result of half backed graduates that Nigeria institutions turn out every year, the rate of unemployment has continued to rise. It is a well-known issue that no economy in the world no matter how viable, will be able to completely grow and be sustained without well trained and educated one's, hence the need to adequately take care of our educational sectors. Madaki (2019) alluded that corruption in the education sector has more serious implication for the country in general because it short-changes members of the society in its provision of their fundamental human rights of social service. Corruption encourages mediocrity, impacts orderliness, abandons merits and equal competition which goes against the objectives of education in global stage. The study established that corruption in educational sector has engineered the feeling of frustration, disgruntlement, immorality, militancy, infrastructural deficits, poverty and lack of foreign investment. Ngita Njoka and Ndegwa (2019) submitted that corruption in education portends a bleak future by withdrawing from people their worth. Rewarding unmerited achievement and normalizing society mistrust. Similarly, corruption and poor governance are a major impediment to the

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realization of the right to education. Corruption is one of the most problematic forces in the world that intuitively undercuts the expected education gains in all social and economic areas. Chatham house (2021) maintained that in societies where corruption is widespread, and where children witness authority figures such as parent and educators engaging in corrupt practices, the value of integrity is eroded. Jarome and Anekwe, (2022) Opined that corruption in tertiary institutions have far-reaching consequences. It jeopardizes the provision of qualitative education for the citizenry, there by leading to drop in tertiary education standard.

Social Studies Education Panacea for Tackling Corruption in Nigeria

Edinyang and Usang (2012) used the philosophy and Objectives Social Studies education and concluded that Social studies is a value free and value laden subject with the capacity to build sound morals and integrity in all facets of the society and that the subject has five unique ways of bulldozing corruption in Nigeria: exposing students to socio-civic competence and effective citizenship, inculcation of worthy attitude and habits, use of enter-educate institutional mode, Social content area and finally using integrated holistic framework. Akintola (2013) maintained that Social Studies education is an avenue for providing young people with a feeling of hope in the future and confidence in their ability to solve the social and environment problems of individuals, their country, state or nation. This implies that Social Studies has all it takes to solve the problems that is affecting the society such as corruption, insurgency, banditry, kidnapping.etc. Ogunwu (2016) maintained that corruption can be fought through re-orientation of values, development of positive attitudes that transform the moral qualities and consciousness of the individual and the entire society. More importantly the role of Social Studies teacher in curbing corruption cannot be underscored. The teacher is the most influential and life changing model as she/he is practically with the students teaching them society core values. Like Germany, Singapore and America are built on trust, discipline, liberty, equality and free enterprise Nigeria cherished values include integrity contentment, discipline and service. All these can be inculcated into the learners through using the instrumentality of Social Studies. Omale Mumini and Salisu (2018) Submitted that Social Studies education by virtue of its nature and content is able to bring about the desired change and national transformation because it places a premium on corruption prevention, avoidance, resistance, non-indulgence or abhorrence via right character propelled self-discipline as against coercive discipline of the anti-corruption efforts or commissions. Proper teaching and learning of value contents in Social Studies will not only improve conceptualization of values but will also curtail other societal ills such as excessive materialism, examination malpractice, cultism, corruption, Social and political differences in Nigeria. Adebayo Olatunde and Obaje (2020) opined that Social Studies education teaches the practice of virtue, values, skills which is the ultimate route to behavior change or modification that could reduce corrupt practices among teachers in Nigeria junior secondary.

Conclusion

Based on the paper, corruption had a great implication to the educational and socio-economic development in Nigeria at basic level of education. Which made some teachers and schools to collect gifts from the students which resulted in producing unproductive graduate that cannot move the country forward to achieve economic growth. Therefore, the paper concluded that greediness and selfishness of some people entrusted with positions of authority to serve the people and also the political interferences with bad leadership of not doing the right things to the people such as protecting the life's and properties, provision of social services, taking care of the welfare of the workers, salary increment among others are the major causes of corruption in Nigeria. This is why Social Studies education become a necessary tool which if effectively use to inculcate positives attitudes and values of loving one's country coupled with contentment and integrity the corruption will be tackle in Nigeria.

Recommendations

The following suggestion were made in respect of this paper to tackle corruption in Nigeria at basic level of education.

1. **Attitudinal Change:** There is need for change in behavior people should learn to good and discard their old ways of attaching much value to worldly materials. Instead they should be contented with the little they have and allowed peace to reign for one's betterment and that of the society.
2. **Strict and Severe Punishment:** Government as a matter of urgency should give autonomy to the anti-graft agency and court to do their job without interferences. This will make possible the perpetrators of corruption to face the law of the land irrespective of their class, gender, religion or political affiliations.
3. **Welfare Package:** There is need for both the Government and Private employers to take adequate care of the welfare of their staff's rewards, increase salaries. This will motivate the workers to put in their best not only that it will also make them not to delve in corruption.

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4. **Good Leadership:** The Leaders should ensure that they provide good leadership to their subjects such as protecting the lives and properties of the citizens, and social services etc. when leaders are doing the right things and declare zero tolerance in corruption citizens will dare not involve in corruption.
5. **Teaching of Social Studies:** There is need to teach and prioritize the national values (discipline, tolerance, integrity, contentment, honesty and patriotism, etc.) embedded in the Social Studies content which will help to tackle the problem of corruption in Nigeria.
6. **Creating Awareness on the dangers of corruption:** There is need to embark on massive campaigns by the government, civil society organizations to educate the people dangers posed by this ugly diseases (corruption) this could be done via different media such as radio, televisions, online etc.

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